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UNSPOKEN BUT HEARD: COMMUNICATION BARRIERS OF INDIVIDUALS WITH SPEECH DISORDERS

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ABSTRACT

This study explored the communication barriers experienced by individual with speech disorder in the Municipality of Abuyog, Leyte using a Single Case research design. Data were collected and analysed to capture the live challenges experienced by the participant who relies on gestures and nonverbal communication in day-to-day living. Grounded on Piaget's Cognitive Development Theory (1936), which linked speech development to stages of cognitive growth. Speech problem may arise from delay or difficulties in these stages, highlighting the need to address both cognitive and language development in intervention. According to the US National Institute on Deafness and other Communication Disorders, 6 to 8 million people of the total population of the United States have speech impairment. If we extrapolate that to the world population which is calculated to 7.9 billion people (United Nations Worldometer) this suggests that over 170 million individuals may have speech impairments. Additionally, the study of Wray et al. (2016) showed that while children with language impairments produced gestures at similar rates to typically developing peers, the gestures were less informative and integrated. This implies that the effectiveness of communication depends on how well they supplement or replace verbal language.

Findings revealed that gesture and nonverbal communication enhanced basic interaction, connection to others, and expression of needs. Results emphasize the needs of family members, educators, and communities to recognize the role of communication barriers in bridging the gaps towards individual with speech problem. This study addresses the gap in localized on communication barriers in Philippine rural settings and offer implications for developing an inclusive approach to support the social integration of individual with speech problem.

Keywords: *Speech disorders, communication barrier, nonverbal communication, gesture, interaction*

INTRODUCTION

Speech disorder is an impairment of speech communication that prevents the transmission of idea and feelings (Merriam-Webster Dictionary 2025). The study of Carbonero (2022) reveals that more than 170 million people in the world have speech impairment. This substantial number underscores the widespread impact of these conditions on individuals, families, and communities. These difficulties affect not only personal expression but also academic achievement, career opportunities, and social inclusion. If left unaddressed, speech impairment can lead to frustration, isolation, and long-term barriers, education and community participation.

In the Philippines context, limited attention has been given to support individual with speech problem, particularly in rural communities as Law et al. (2015) point out, speech-language disorder interfered with one's process of normal communication and are one of the most reported disorders in the childhood stage of a child. Many children and adults with conditions such as mutism or cleft palate

encounter significant challenges in being understood, which restrict their ability to learn and socialized. These realities underscore the urgent need for inclusive strategies that recognize alternative mode of expression.

Nonverbal communication, particularly gesture, provide a powerful bridge when spoken language is absent or impaired. Long before spoken language developed, human relies on gestures to convey messages, meaning and emotions (Hewes, 1999). Today's research shows that gestures not only supplement communication but also foster participation, social connection, and emotional well-being (Meadow, 2003), like Abuyog, Leyte.

Moreover, the absence of structured support for individual with speech problem in such localities deepen their marginalization. The Municipality focused only on giving support to the Senior citizens, 4p's beneficiaries, individuals with physical disabilities, tricycle drivers, and farmers, neglecting these individuals with speech disorders. This neglect perpetuates their exclusion from social interaction and limits their opportunities and growth. In this connection, the researchers, driven by the need to uncover the benefits and challenges of using gestures or nonverbal communication in social contexts, ultimately to inform the development of more effective gestures or nonverbal communication interventions and support strategies for individuals with speech disorders.

The findings aimed to highlight the importance of integrating gestures and nonverbal strategies of individual/s with speech problem in daily life, in education, and in opportunity to engage fully and meaningfully in society.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

This study aimed to explore on the lived experiences of an individual with speech disorder. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What communication barriers do individuals with speech disorders face in different settings?
2. How will it affect their mental health?
3. What are the dilemmas or challenges faced by these individuals?
4. Why does gestures or nonverbal communication important to the social interactions of individuals with speech disorders?
5. How will the government (local, national) and NGO can help those individuals with speech disorders?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design.

This study used a single-case design to explore the unique experiences of an individual with a speech disorder. Following Beale (1995). This approach enables an in-depth examination of a specific situation, capturing the participant's lived experiences in detail. Focusing on one person allowed for a rich understanding of how gestures and nonverbal communication influenced his social interactions and relationships.

Research Instrument

Data were collected through an in-depth interview and direct observation of the participant. The interview guide, based on Kvale and Brinkmann (2009), encouraged open sharing while allowing follow-up questions. It focused on the participant's use of gestures and nonverbal communication, as well as the challenges and benefits of these strategies. To enhance data richness, field notes, video recordings, and observations captured both verbal and nonverbal cues for comprehensive analysis.

Validation of Research Instrument.

To ensure the instrument's face validity, the questions were developed based on their relevance to the research objectives. In addition, the research adviser reviewed the interview guide to confirm that the questions were appropriate and suitable for exploring the experiences of individuals with speech disorders.

Locale of the Study

The research was conducted in Abuyog, Leyte- a 5th District of Leyte. The researchers opted to choose this locale because the participant is a resident of this municipality, and this made therefore reaching out to participant become easier to provide an appropriate context for data collection.

Research Participants

Using purposive sampling, one individual from Abuyog, Leyte, who has a speech disorder and relies on gestures and nonverbal communication, was selected. The participant is thirty-two years of age, male, single and currently working at local printing shop as a layout artist. This focus on a single participant provided in-depth insights into his lived experiences, emphasizing the challenges he encountered and how gestures influenced his social interactions and relationships.

Data Analysis

Narrative analysis was used to examine interview transcripts, observations, and field notes, identifying key stories about the participant's use of gestures and nonverbal communication. This method centered the participant's physical condition and provided deeper insight into how these strategies shaped his social interactions and daily life.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researchers secured permission from the authorities and obtained informed consent from the participant and his parent. This ensured that participation was voluntary and that they clearly understood the purpose of the research and their rights. The interviews were conducted in a respectful and comfortable setting, supported by direct observations, video recordings, and detailed field notes. A closed observation with the participant was also carried out to gain a clearer understanding of his natural responses and behaviour in a more personal setting. After the data collection, the interviews and recordings were transcribed, and all materials were organized for careful review and analysis.

Ethical Considerations

This study carefully followed ethical standards to protect the participant and uphold research integrity. Before the data collection, the participant and his parent were fully informed about the study's purpose, process, possible risks, and benefits. Signed consent forms were obtained to confirm voluntary participation, with the freedom to withdraw at any time without consequences. The research procedures were reviewed and approved by the adviser to ensure they met ethical requirements. Confidentiality and anonymity were strictly observed, and all personal information was kept secure in line with the Data Privacy Act of 2012.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The following themes emerged after a careful data analyzation.

Bullied in School Due to Speech Difficulty

The participant described how he was often misjudged as inattentive or unwilling due to his difficulty articulating clearly, which caused him to withdraw and become more isolated. He said,

"Nagkukuri ako pagkig-estorya saak mga classmate han time nga na eskwela pa ako labi na san elementary pa ako, kay diri gud ako na intindihan sin tuhay san akun mga classmate tungod san akun kaistorya" ("I had a hard time talking with my classmates back when I was still in school, especially during elementary, because they couldn't really understand me well because of the way I speak").

Moreover, the participant's father recalled, *"Mas naluoy ako han akon anak han panahon nga na eskwela pa hiya kay ginbully hiya hit iya iba nga mga classmate tungod la hit iya kaestorya Kay may mga time na nauli hiya ha balay tikang eskwelahan nga nagtitanangis"* ("I felt sorry for my child when he was still in school because he was being bullied by his classmates just because of his being talkative. There were times when he would come home from school crying").

Inner Strength Amid Challenges

In an interview, the participant shared instances where communication difficulties led to misunderstandings, frustration, and reduced engagement in academic and workplace settings. These barriers often resulted in misjudgement or exclusion, leading to social withdrawal. Shannon and Weaver's Communication Model (1948) emphasizes clear channels and minimal noise for effective communication. In this case, "noise" is both internal (articulation difficulties due to cleft palate) and external (misinterpretation), disrupting the intended message.

The participant also expressed the emotional impact of ongoing communication difficulties. He experienced a loss of confidence, particularly during adolescence, when social belonging was crucial. Fear of judgment and self-consciousness about his speech contributed to anxiety, leading to episodes of sadness and disconnection. He said *"Tungod san akun kundisyun na warayan ako sin gana ngan nawarayan sin tapud sa kalugaringun nga umabut sa punto na diri na ako nag gawas-gawas ngan nag ka mayda ako sin anxiety."* ("Because of my condition, I lost motivation and self-confidence to the point that I stopped going out and developed anxiety."). Despite these struggles, he demonstrated resilience by developing coping mechanisms, including self-reflection and positive affirmations to rebuild self-esteem. He noted, *"Bisan may mga tawo nga nadiri ha akon, nga nagbully ha akon, diri ko nala ginpapansin. Instead ginhimo ko siya rason para mas ugupan ngan mas dawaton ko pa tak kalugaringon"* ("Even if there are people who dislike me, who bully me, I no longer pay attention to them. Instead, I made it as a reason to love myself more and accept myself more"). His father stated, *"Pero labaw sa tanan, bilib ako sit akon anak kay tungod bisan ano ka kakuri sit iya gin-again, nagpabilin la gihap hiya nga may tapod ha iya kalugaringun, ha Ginoo, ngan nagpabilin hiya nga maupay na pagkatawo"* ("But above all, I admire my child because despite facing many challenges, he still remains steadfast with faith in himself, in God, and remains a good person").

Social Dilemmas

The participant described social dilemmas, finding it difficult to navigate interactions in crowded or fast-paced settings, such as school events, public spaces, or family gatherings, which triggered discomfort and uncertainty. He said, *"Diri ako nakadtu sin lugar na damo it tawo like mga party kay tungod gin lilikayan ko makipag estorya sa mga tawo tungod sit akun sitwasyon."* ("I don't go to places with a lot of people, like parties, because I avoid talking to others due to my situation"). This tension between fear of rejection and longing for connection reflects the emotional complexity experienced by individuals with speech disorders in social situations.

His father noted, *"May mga time na naluluoy ako hit akon anak tungod kay diri niya naienjoy it iya kinabuhi parehas ha iba"*. ("There are times when I feel sorry for my child because he doesn't enjoy his life like others do"). This shows how his cleft palate affects his social life. Despite negative

experiences, he also shared moments of empathy and patience from others, reinforcing the possibility of acceptance and inclusion: *“Pero bisan pa man may mga tawo nga nadiri ha akon, may mga tawo pa gihap nga dumawat ha akon ngan ginbigugma ako despite of my flaws like an akon father ngan friends”* (“But even if there are people who dislike me, there are still people who accept me and love me despite my flaws, like my father and friends”).

Gesture Dependent

The participant depended on gestures and nonverbal communication like pointing, facial expressions, and miming to aid his verbal speech in daily interactions. These gestures were mostly improvised and understood mainly by those close to him. Although aware of American Sign Language (ASL), he had no formal training due to limited support but advocates for ASL to be formally introduced, especially in schools and workplaces in rural areas. He said, *“Naggamit ako sin aksyon kun mag estorya para maintindihan gihap ako, like for example may gusto ko nga bagay nga diri gud nira na intidihan, it akun nala ginbubuhay kay gintutudlo ko nala para la maintindihan nira”* (“I use actions when I talk so that I can still be understood. For example, if there is something I want but they do not really understand me, I use gestures instead of speaking so they can understand me better”). This shows how crucial gestures are to his communication as both a student and worker. He noted that combining verbal and nonverbal methods was more effective than relying on either alone, reflecting his adaptive approach. This aligns with Goldin-Meadow’s (2003) view that gestures are vital to communication, helping clarify ideas when speech is impaired

Deprived of Support System

The participant shared that the only support he received was a PWD identification card, with no additional financial assistance as he disclosed *“Waray man kami nadadawat nga financial assistance para hadton mga tawo na parehas ha akon nga may mga problema ha pag estorya or bisan na manla batas nga nagwewelcome fully para sa amon nga may problema sa pag estorya like sa workplace ngan sa eskwelahan”* (“We don’t receive any financial assistance for people like me who have speech problems or even just a welcoming attitude towards us who have speech problems, whether in the workplace or in school”). He was unaware of government or NGO programs and stressed the need for equal opportunities in education and employment, saying, *“It akon la gin aampo is magkamay-ada kami oportunidad nga makadawat hin pantay na oportunidad pag abot hit pankarawat ha trabaho kay may nahibaruan ngan skills man gihap kami parehas hit iba nga mga tawo na normal it kaestorya”* (“All I pray for is that we have the opportunity to receive equal opportunities in terms of employment because we also have knowledge and skills just like other people who speak normally”). Furthermore, he advocated for the introduction of formal standard sign language in rural communities, expressing, *“Ngan usa pa, para mas maintindihan gud kami hit mas durudamo nga mga tawo diri la it amon pamilya ngan close namon, kundi pati gihap it iba nga tawo is sana ig introduced gihap ha amon lugar especially sa mga rural areas hin formal an standard sign language”* (“And also, for more people to understand us, not just our family and close ones, but also other people, I hope that formal standard sign language is introduced in our place, especially in our areas

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The findings reveal that living with a speech disorder is not only about the challenge of speaking, but also about coping with the social and emotional difficulties that come with it. Gestures and other forms of nonverbal communication emerged as vital tools for connection, showing that

meaningful expression goes beyond spoken words. These insights point to the urgent need for better support systems that promote inclusion and dignity for individuals with speech disorders.

Based on these results, it is recommended that local governments and institutions introduce structured sign language programs in schools and communities, particularly in areas where resources are limited. Consistent financial support should be provided to sustain these initiatives, alongside free or subsidized training for families, educators, and community leaders. Long-term efforts such as scholarships, livelihood opportunities, and awareness campaigns are also encouraged to break down barriers and ensure that persons with speech disorders are given equal opportunities to thrive.

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